

ENHANCED PERFORMANCE IN ISPS THROUGH OPTIMIZED DNS CLUSTERING WITH RESPONSE POLICY ZONES

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ABSTRACT. *Filtering negative content such as online gambling, pornography, hoaxes, and terrorism is an obligation that ISPs in Indonesia must carry out. The filtering system adopted by the Indonesian Government involves blocking domains that are indicated to contain negative content. The blocking of negative content results in a decline in ISP service performance due to the continuously increasing number of blocked domains. One solution that can filter negative content domain access by ISP customers is DNS with Response Policy Zones (RPZ) features. For the RPZ feature to function as DNS filtering, a blacklist of domains in text file format is required. The file is a zone file in DNS managed by the Indonesian Government and is named the trustpositif file. The trustpositif file, used as a zone file in DNS filtering, is automatically sent by the Government DNS server to all registered ISP DNS servers. This research will compare implementing a single zone trustpositif file with multiple zone files in trustpositif file for the single zone RPZ uses a file directly sent from the Government DNS server. Meanwhile, the multiple zones RPZ uses a trustpositif file divided into ten files using a clustering method. This experiment was tested with 500 domains on a virtual machine with single and multiple zone configurations. The measurements were taken using the tools dig and dnslookup. The experiment results measured with the dig tool showed that RPZ multiple zones are 10.7% faster than a single zone, and dnslookup is 9.4% faster.*

Keywords: DNS filtering, DNS firewall, Response Policy Zones (RPZ), Clustering zones

1. Introduction. The development of digital technology in the world today is progressing rapidly. On the other hand, Internet crime is also evolving and becoming increasingly sophisticated over time. Like the Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks reported by NetScout [1] in 2023, which recorded 13 million attacks, Cloudflare [2] reported 8.5 million in the first half of 2024. In addition to DDoS attacks, phishing is the most common Internet crime, deceiving victims into providing personal information on websites, emails, and text messages sent by the perpetrators. Phishing can be mitigated through various methods, including educating individuals on detection and prevention, implementing Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) for access to online services, and employing Domain Name Service (DNS) filtering to block domains recognized as phishing sites by Internet Service Providers (ISPs).

The Domain Name System (DNS) is a vital element for Internet Service Providers (ISPs) in converting domain names into IP (Internet Protocol) addresses. DNS is also an essential component in protecting the nation and state from elements of ideology, doctrine, pornography, hoaxes, online gambling, and various negative content. In Indonesia, ISPs are obligated to filter domains that fall into the category of negative content (Gambling, Fraud, Terrorism/Radicalism, Intellectual Property Rights, Information Security

Breaches, Hoaxes, Pornography, and Sector Agencies) as regulated by law and supervised by the Indonesian Government. In May 2024, 232,273 were blocked by the Indonesian Government. Out of the total filtered domains, approximately 99.54% are domains categorized as online gambling. The filtering method used by the Indonesian Ministry of Communication and Information is through the Response Policy Zones (RPZ) feature in DNS [5-7]. The zone file transfer process can be seen in Figure 1, which is a *trustpositif* file (domain blacklist file) that will be sent through the government DNS server to all ISPs in Indonesia. The capacity of the file sent to all ISPs is huge; for example, the file on 14 August, 2024 was 711 megabytes (MiB), with a total of 16,794,755 lines.

FIGURE 1. Flow transfer file RPZ from Government DNS

With the increasing number of domains growing daily, the *trustpositif* file is becoming more extensive, which increases DNS query time. The increase in DNS query time is because the queried domains must be verified in the *trustpositif* file. This process causes the user experience of browsing the Internet to deteriorate due to slow DNS queries. For this reason, there is a need for a solution to speed up DNS queries with filtering features against domains that contain negative content, which continues to grow. One solution to accelerate DNS queries is through clustering in the zone file.

Filtering negative content aside from DNS has been researched by Jung et al. [8] using the Server Name Indication (SNI) method. This method compares the domain to be accessed to see if it is on the blacklist of the surveillance server. Filtering with the SNI method can be bypassed with ESNI (Encrypted SNI), which encrypts the SNI and Virtual Private Network (VPN). In addition, Ichise et al. [7] studied DNS filtering by comparing the query speed of the MySQL method, which stores filtered domain data, and RPZ for domain checking, followed by filtering done by OpenFlow. From the test data obtained using the *dig* tool for DNS queries, the RPZ method was faster than MySQL. An essential issue in previous research was the slow speed in accessing filtered domain data, whether using the SNI method or RPZ, without bypassing the filtering.

In several previous DNS filtering studies, the RPZ feature available in DNS was used to store domain data in the RPZ zone file [7,16,17]. By default, the RPZ file on the DNS server is a single file, so as the list of domains grows, the query time will increase. Our work will investigate DNS query speed by comparing single and multiple zones in RPZ, where the zone file is in text format that stores the blacklist of domains to be filtered. Next, using the tools *dig* and *dnslookup*, data will be collected for the experiment of querying domains on the DNS server with single and multiple zones. This research was conducted at Jakarta's ISP, which serves customers with satellite, radio, and fiber optic communication media throughout Indonesia.

2. Literature Review.

2.1. Domain Name Services (DNS). DNS is a fundamental element of Internet Service Providers (ISPs) for converting domain names into IP (Internet Protocol) addresses [5,10]. Many applications and protocols rely on DNS, such as email using IMAP, POP3, and SMTP protocols, as well as web browsers using HTTP/HTTPS. Based on its function, DNS is divided into two types: authoritative DNS and resolver/recursive DNS. Authoritative DNS is the server that stores mapping information from domain to IP or vice versa. The DNS Resolver functions as a proxy, providing the information requested by the client from the authoritative DNS. The information returned by the DNS resolver can be incorrect when filtering negative content domains or cybercrime. There are three types of DNS resolvers: Public DNS, managed by companies or organizations like Google and Cloudflare for anyone to use; ISP DNS, managed by ISPs and used only by their customers; and Open DNS, which is used solely for experimental purposes [5].

2.2. Security threat. Many attacks or threats originate from the Internet in today's increasingly advanced digital world. Several Internet attacks that use DNS to carry out their assaults include DDoS attacks with the DNS Amplification Attack method, which exploits vulnerabilities in DNS by sending multiplied traffic to the target, DNS Reflection Attacks that involve IP spoofing to attack the target, and Bogus Domain Attack (NXDOMAIN) that sends fake addresses to DNS to slow down server responses. In addition to DDoS attack methods, some attacks change the IP of certain domains. For example, DNS Spoofing manipulates fake domains in the DNS cache, and DNS Hijacking alters domains on the server to redirect traffic [13].

Social engineering attacks are another type of attack that employs domains to execute attacks. Phishing, romance scams, baiting, reverse social engineering, thread hijacking, and scareware are among the various social engineering attacks. To gain access to computers or similar devices, this attack typically manipulates victims into providing confidential information, such as passwords or One-Time Passwords (OTPs) [14]. The method of attack is spreading phishing emails or messages that contain a fake Uniform Resource Locator (URL) so that the victim clicks on it and then enters a phony website. Because the victim is unaware of the fake website, they enter confidential information such as their username and password into that site. One malware attack also uses fake domains or URLs with a distribution method like phishing. The malware will propagate throughout the victim's network once the victim clicks on the infected URL.

2.3. Response Policy Zones (RPZ). Prevention of phishing attacks, which spread through fake emails or text messages that lure victims into clicking on fraudulent URLs, can be achieved by using DNS filtering. The feature in DNS is called Response Policy Zones (RPZ) [3,4,7,16,17], which serves to redirect domains identified as phishing, malware, and negative content to a landing page containing information that the domain has been blocked. DNS RPZ, or DNS Firewall, was initially a filtering feature only implemented in the BIND application. ISPs and hosting companies are widely used as authoritative and resolver DNS. BIND was developed by the Internet System Consortium (ISC) and is distributed for free. The RPZ feature has been implemented in BIND since version 9.8. The configuration in the Zones file for RPZ allows DNS to change the domain policy by adding a CNAME parameter to point to a specific domain or NXDOMAIN, which makes the domain non-existent. The zone files in the BIND application can be created as multiple files with a maximum of 64 files in a single instance.

3. Research Methods.

3.1. Research stages. The experiment of filtering negative content in this research uses a DNS server, and the feature employed is Response Policy Zones (RPZ). If the RPZ feature is to function, a domain blacklist in the form of a text file is required. This file, known as the *trustpositif* file, contains a blacklist of domains issued by the Government as a reference file for DNS servers that have been adjusted according to applicable regulations. To address the issues in this research, it will be divided into 4 stages as shown in Figure 2 as follows.

- **Overview.** The overview begins with the background of the research, followed by the objectives, identified problems, and scope of this study. Literature research is also being conducted better to understand the state of research on this topic.
- **Experiment.** Proceeding with the experimental phase by designing the topology for the experimental environment, the experimental phase begins by configuring the primary DNS resolver to obtain the trust file with synchronization from the Government DNS server. After that, a Virtual Machine (VM) will be built for experiments in DNS RPZ research.
- **Data collection.** At this stage, experiments will be conducted on the VM, and the results will be collected for analysis in the next stage.
- **Evaluation.** The data that has been collected will be processed and evaluated at this stage.

FIGURE 2. Research stages diagram

3.2. Topology. The topology configuration in the experimental setting is illustrated in Figure 3. In the experimental environment, 2 Virtual Machines (VM) and 1 notebook are prepared with the specifications listed in Table 1. VM1 will be used for experiments with a single-zone RPZ, and VM2 will be used for experiments with multiple-zone RPZ. Once everything is ready, this research experiment begins when the Primary DNS resolver obtains the *trustpositif* file from the Government DNS server. The Primary DNS used to acquire the *trustpositif* file is the DNS resolver server that serves ISP customers at the location where this research is conducted. The *trustpositif* file will be automatically sent

FIGURE 3. Research environment topology

TABLE 1. Test environment specification

	Virtual machine	Notebook
CPU	2	M1 Pro
RAM (GiB)	4	16
O/S	ubuntu 22.04.02 LTS	macOS Sonoma 14.5
Tools	BIND version 9.18.28	<i>dig</i> and <i>dnslookup</i>

to the Primary DNS whenever there is a change in the Government DNS server. This *trustpositif* file will be used in the research experiments.

From the topology in Figure 3, the *trustpositif* file is automatically received from the Government DNS server to the primary DNS ISP. This file is then copied to the */etc/bind/* directory on VM1 and used as the zone file for RPZ. The RPZ zone file on VM2 is from the Primary DNS that has been processed with a script before being copied to VM2. The clustering begins by reading the number of rows in the file and dividing the total number by 10. With the VM conditions in Table 1 used in the research being quite minimal, the file is divided into 10. The first ten rows, the file’s header, will not be counted in the division process and will be stored as the header. This header contains the serial number of the Start Of Authority (SOA) record, which must be the same in all files. The divided files will have the header added to each file. The processed files will be copied to VM2 in the directory */etc/bind/*. Once everything is ready, the notebook collects data by performing DNS queries from the prepared list of domains.

3.3. Data collection. The *trustpositif* file used in this experiment is taken on 12 February 2024, containing 5,489,440 domains and 10,959,788 lines in the file. The size of this file is 457,299,410 bytes, which is a text (txt) file that will be copied to VM1. For VM2, the average size of the *trustpositif* files that have undergone clustering is 45,730,312 bytes. The average file per line is 1,095,990, and the number of domains is 547,995. The specification information for the *trustpositif* file for each VM can be found in Table 2.

The filtered domains are redirected using the CNAME command to the domain *laman-labuh.aduankonten.id*, a landing page created by the Government that contains a notification that the domain has been blocked. The SOA serial number will always increase to a value greater than the previous one whenever there is a change in the *trustpositif* file. This change will cause the *trustpositif* file on the DNS resolver server at each ISP to change automatically. The DNS System application used in this research is BIND, an

TABLE 2. *trustpositif* file specification in VM

	Single zone (VM1)	Multiple zone (VM2)
Number of files	1	10
File size (byte)	457,299,410	45,730,312
Number of lines/files	10,959,788	1,095,990
Number of domains/files	5,489,440	547,995

Open Source application developed by ISC. To activate RPZ on VM1 and VM2, it is necessary to configure the *named.conf.options* file located in the */etc/bind/* directory. This file adds the response-policy configuration with the *trustpositif* zone to redirect to the ISP notification landing page using the CNAME parameter.

The next step is to add the configuration in the *trustpositif* zone to point to the *trustpositif* file copied to VM1 in the */etc/bind/* directory. In the *trustpositif* zone, it is necessary to add the parameter type master because the *trustpositif* file is stored in the VM's local storage. For VM2, the response-policy configuration is created with 10 zones to establish multiple zones within the *named.conf.options* file. Then, ten zones named "*trustpositif1*" to "*trustpositif10*" are added, each pointing to their respective files *trustpositif1* to *trustpositif10*, which have been divided using a clustering method.

The data collection uses tools such as *dig* (domain information groper) and *dnslookup* [19]. The tool *dig* is automatically installed by default in Unix-based operating systems such as Ubuntu, RedHat, macOS, and Debian. Meanwhile, *dnslookup* must first be installed on the notebook by downloading the source code from GitHub. The test domain's query time results will be collected using both tools.

The data collection in this research will use 500 domains for experiments on VM1 with single zones and VM2 with multiple zones. Out of the total 500 domains used for the experiments, 250 domains are not included in the *trustpositif* file, and 250 domains are included in the *trustpositif* blacklist file. For the data collection process, 30 trials will be conducted for 500 domains on VM1 and VM2. The data collection will utilize a Python script to automate the execution of the *dig* and *dnslookup* commands in the notebook. The experiment results will be saved in an Excel file and then processed to be summed and divided by 30 for each domain. The average value in each domain is obtained from that division, which is then totaled and divided by the number of domains. The results of the data calculation process from the experiments on VM1 and VM2 will be used for evaluation.

4. Result and Discussion. This research began with the preparation of virtual machines, namely VM1 and VM2. Once the virtual machines were ready, we collected query time data over 3 days, with details of 5 data collections in the morning followed by 5 data collections in the afternoon. Experiments were conducted with 500 domains in each collection using the tools *dig* and *dnslookup* on VM1 and VM2. The sample results of the data collection will be displayed in Table 3. Table 3 provides six examples of domains from 500 tested domains. The data sample in Table 3 consists of three filtered domains and three unfiltered domains. The query time data in Table 3 consists of 4 columns divided into

- Single-dig is the average value of single zone trials using the dig.
- Multiple-dig is the average value of multiple zone trials using the dig.
- Single-dnslookup is the average value of single zone trials using the dnslookup.
- Multiple-dnslookup is the average value of multiple zone trials using the dnslookup.

Any anomalous values have been removed from the collected query time data to ensure a more accurate analysis.

TABLE 3. Sample result testing VM1 and VM2 with *dig* and *dnslookup*

Domain	Query time (ms)			
	Single-dig	Multiple-dig	Single-dnslookup	Multiple-dnslookup
traveloka.com	44.867	34.600	103.893	73.117
agoda.com	8.233	10.000	24.029	25.466
booking.com	47.633	23.500	87.617	70.248
pornhub.com	7.700	6.933	26.963	39.956
acetoto888.online	10.500	11.700	22.063	19.527
agen86.org	6.600	7.667	42.566	43.726

The experimental conditions in the virtual machine shown in Table 3 were conducted without queries other than those from the notebook. Thus, if the traffic query load on the virtual machine increases, the experiment results can be affected. In addition, hardware can also affect DNS query time results by replacing virtual machines with bare metal servers.

TABLE 4. Results of the comparison of the average time of single and multiple zones

Tools	Single zone (VM1) (ms)	Multiple zones (VM2) (ms)	Changes (%)
<i>dnslookup</i>	55.944	50.673	9.422
<i>dig</i>	35.534	31.731	10.704

5. Conclusions. One way to control and manage domains containing negative content, such as online gambling, pornography, terrorism, and hoaxes, is to use DNS filtering. RPZ is one DNS filtering feature used to manage these domains. DNS filtering with RPZ requires a *trustpositif* file as a blacklist of domains. The list of domains in this file continues to grow, which increases the query time in DNS. Therefore, this research employs a clustering method for files in DNS RPZ to address the issue of DNS query time. The experimental results in our work show that the query time measured with the *dig* tool in single zone and multiple zones of DNS RPZ indicates that the multiple zones clustering method is 10.7% faster. Additionally, measurements with the *dnslookup* tool show that multiple zones are 9.42% faster. It can be concluded that the clustering method in DNS with multiple zones can accelerate DNS query time. Thus, this method can help ISPs improve the speed of Internet service performance, which is free from negative content. This research can be continued by dividing the *trustpositif* files into more, up to a maximum of 64. The files can also be clustered based on the initial letter, domain category, and domain length.

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